

THE FAIRY TALE GENRE OF FOLKLORE

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Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada xalq og'zaki ijodining ertak janri va uning tarbiyaviy ahamiyati, ularda aks etuvchi milliy an'ana va qadriyatlar, o'ziga xos xususiyatlar aks etgan. Shuningdek, ertak atamasining kelib chiqishi va turli hududlardagi nomlari haqida atroflicha fikr yuritilgan.

Annotation

This article describes the fairy tale genre of folklore and its educational significance, national traditions and values reflected in them, and its specific features. Also, the origin of the term "fairy tale" and its names in different regions are discussed in detail.

Аннотация

В данной статье описывается сказочный жанр фольклора и его воспитательное значение, отраженные в них национальные традиции и ценности, его специфические особенности. Также подробно обсуждается происхождение термина «сказка» и его названия в разных регионах.

Basic concepts:

Fairy tale, folklore, ancient Turkic language, prose, prose rhyme, patriotism and humanitarianism, thinking, self-awareness, research.

A fairy tale is one of the most ancient and popular types of Uzbek folklore, it is a genre of magic, adventure and household character based on weaving and fiction. The methods of studying and researching fairy tales in world folklore studies have been constantly updated. The history of the origin of fairy tales goes back to the ancient stone age. If religion originated from people's different perspective on life, interest in nature, and striving for self-awareness, then in a sense, this was the impetus for the emergence of the genre of fairy tales. Fairy tales were a means of introducing people's values, customs and history and passing them down from generation to generation. There are different views on the formation of the term fairy tale in different periods:

1. The term fairy tale is used in the style of "mature" in Mahmud Koshgari's "Devoni dictionary of Turks": "Etuk is a story, a fairy tale; this word is also used

to convey a purpose to the king, to tell a story. It is derived from the story of something.

2. The word "ertak" is composed of the suffix "tak", which means that it is similar to the word "ir" ("yir", "jir"), "similar to a song" means. Because the beginning of fairy tales with saj (prose rhyme) acquires melody. Also, some fairy tales (such as "Musicha", "Yoriltash") contain poetic parts. But poetic passages are rarely found in Uzbek folk tales. Therefore, the fairy tale is an example of folk prose. Since fairy tales are told by ordinary people, not all of them contain poetic parts or prose fragments. In the ancient Turks, a fairy tale was "ir" or "yir", and in the time of the great thinker Alisher Navoi, it meant an oral story or epic, and in this regard, he wrote down the following information:

Ey yirov, sen ham ishingni ko'rguz,
Yotug'on birla ulug' irni tuz¹.

It should be noted that the composition "ulug' ir" mentioned by Navoi actually has the meaning of an epic, which was performed by a yirov (bakhshi) accompanied by a yotugon (dombira). Yirov still means the performer of folk epics. In addition, the word "iztek" in Ottoman Turks and "irtek", which is used by Bashkirs today, that is, the word epic consisting of prose and verse, still represents that historical layer. Through this, it is proved that the term "ulug' ir" belonging to Navoi's pen is the ancient equivalent of the epic genre.

3. Navoi often uses the word "chorchak" in his works, and "ir" corresponds to the characteristics of the term fairy tale, unlike the term epic:

Habibim husni vasfin uyla muhlik anglakim bo'lg'ay,
Qoshinda qissai Yusuf bir uyqu kelturur cho'rchak².

It should also be noted that this word, which was used in the Navoi "chorchak" style, can now be found in Tashkent in the "chopchak" style. So, the word still exists, but it has undergone phonetic changes and changed its form.

The fairy tale is called by different names in different regions of our country. For example, the word "qilinajak karya", meaning tomorrow's story, is "fairy tale" in the southern parts of Namangan, in the form of "matal" in Samarkand, Fergana and Surkhandarya, in the form of "varsoqi" (varsaki) in Khorezm, "ushuk" It is used in Bukhara and in Tashkent. In addition, it is also called a story, a story, an oral story, a story or a story, a myth.

As mentioned above, fairy tales reflect the values, customs and history of the nation. For example, depending on the environment described in fairy tales, it is

¹ Mallayev N.M. Navoiy ijodiyotining xalqchil negizi.-T. 1980.-B.21.

² Alisher Navoiy. MAT. 4-jild. -T.1989. -B.225.

possible to know to which nationality he belongs. For example, the series of scenes in the fairy tale "Turnip" where animals and people eat together at the same table at the end of the fairy tale is not observed in the households of the Uzbek nation. The fairy tale "Boğirsok", which is loved by our people, is considered one of the Russian folk tales, and one of the main characters in it is Boğirsok (in Uzbek people, it could usually be in the form of bread or cake) running away from his grandparents. departure, the fact that bread products have been held very dear by us since ancient times, the old man and the old woman living alone in the fairy tale are the product of a more westernized view. In Western thought, at the age of eighteen, children can live separately from their parents and build their own lives. In the Eastern nations, it is one of our best values that children always live together with their parents and take care of them. Also, the place where the fairy tale is depicted also means which nation the fairy tale belongs to. For example, if the events take place in or around forests and seas, if the images of luxurious castles are given, this shows that the fairy tales are more western. In Uzbek national tales, people are usually engaged in farming and animal husbandry, and the environment of a field or yard is depicted more often.

A fairy tale organizes intuitive knowledge. A fairy tale is not an expression of confidence. This shows that their level of processing is different. A fairy tale is a product of any nation or people, it has a positive effect on the psychology of children, and as a unique educational tool, it serves to further expand the way of thinking, to distinguish between good and evil, and to grow up with feelings of patriotism and humanity.

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